

ISic2879

I.Sicily inscription 2879

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Philosophiana

Place of origin (modern)

near Mazzarino

Provenance

tomb 11, west cemetery, Sofiana (37.31424, 14.29943)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Gela, Museo Archeologico
Regionale di Gela, inventory 38325

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337234

1. ΣΕΚΟ-

2. ὕδα.

3.

4. Οἰκουμε-

5. νία.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175858

EDCS 64300052

PHI 337234

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2002.0614A

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 52.0910A

Bonomi, L. 1964. Cimiteri paleocristiani di Sofiana (retroterra di Gela). *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 40: 169-220. At 206 fig.37

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio.* Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 568

Brugnone, A. 2002. Le iscrizioni. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Panvini, R.(eds.), *La Sicilia centro-merdionale tra il II ed il VI sec. d.C..* Caltanissetta. pp. 295-301. At 296-297 no.2A fig.2

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2879. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387597>